

Spatial Justice Benchmarking

How does Rotterdam consider spatial justice in their urban sustainability transition plans? And how to evaluate it?

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INTRODUCTION & METHODOLOGY

What is Spatial Justice

It involves the fair allocation of burdens and benefits, the attention to processes that do not create or exacerbate inequalities, and the validation and protection of marginalised and vulnerable identities and groups affected by these urban transitions.

Why it matters to climate action

The necessity for Spatial Justice arises from the acknowledgement that space is not a neutral backdrop to human activity but is actively produced, shaped, and contested by social processes, power dynamics, and institutional practices.

The "spatial turn" in the social sciences represents a paradigm shift towards recognising the significance of space in shaping social relations, processes, and outcomes.

Justice must underscore all actions taken to promote sustainability, as it is the foundational virtue of social institutions, just as truth is for systems of thought. Therefore, any law or institution, no matter how efficient or well-organised, must be reformed or abolished if it is unjust (Rawls, 1971)

Poor urban planning and policymaking can exacerbate existing inequalities, concentrating disadvantage in certain areas while privileging others.

Spatial Justice demands a re-evaluation of planning and policy decisions.

How to evaluate

The Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (SJCM) is based on an extensive literature review at the intersection of justice, spatial justice, and planning. The SJCM conceptualizes Spatial Justice by defining applicable components and goals of for each justice dimension (Recognition, Procedural, and Distributive). When approached as an analytical framework, it allows for a structured and comprehensive way of assessing how aspects of spatial justice are considered in planning and design, while drawing attention to the underlying components that build each dimension.

Rotterdam's climate action plan

At a glance:
 The "Rotterdams Weewoord Uitvoeringsagenda 2023-2026" is analysed in this work.

The broader Climate Action Plan of Rotterdam (known as KAR) is regarded as an "agenda-setting" plan with little to no action outlined. One of the tracks is the intersection between climate and the built environment, which is laid out in the "Rotterdams Weewoord Uitvoeringsagenda 2023-2026". This document is analysed in this work.

Rotterdam's climate adaptive agenda for 2023-2026 focuses on developing new real estate, adapting existing buildings, and promoting climate adaptation, energy transition, mobility transition, biodiversity, and circularity. The city aims to prepare for extreme climates, enhance sustainability, and create a healthier living environment through greenery, water storage improvements, and collaborative measures. The goal is to make Rotterdam greener, climate-proof, and healthier for current and future residents with community involvement and partnerships. The city plans to implement 50 climate-adaptive projects in public spaces and integrate climate adaptation measures into urban development, energy transition, and mobility programs, emphasizing sustainable and green solutions.

RESULTS

Balance of VSOA

At a glance:
 The main actions are mostly climate-focused, lacking a more direct social sustainability mention, and focusing on a material or service distribution.

Spatial Justice Assessment

At a glance:
 The weak point is that the RECOGNITION dimension is rarely the focus of the plan. Acknowledgement, validation, protection of individuals, collectives, and communities is not a priority. This is concerning, since climate action should target the most vulnerable and marginalised groups of the city otherwise it might reinforce injustices.

Spatial Justice Scoring

At a glance:
 Every dimension and component has aspects of Spatial Justice in an indirect manner. Given the number of codes, many indirect mentions are balanced by some specific and in-depth aspects. In the document, they are mostly related to the specific area or group that is engaged.

The Spatial Justice Conceptual Model assessed the justice considerations, which now can be scored by the framework built by the Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool.

In general, a score of "-3" means no consideration of spatial justice components, or its aspects. A score of "-1" indicates a general or indirect concern for spatial justice, but it is not a priority. A score of "0" reflects explicit concern for spatial justice in planning, but actions are limited. A score of "+1" denotes specific successful actions, more specific to the area, process, or group. A score of "+3" demonstrates integrated concern with examples, specificity, and indicators for continuous monitoring. Median scores are calculated for each dimension and component from these coded sentences.

Method: The Values, Strategies, Objectives, and Actions (VSOA) methodology is employed to extract core information from the documents. This methodology provides a structure for analysing the key elements of urban plans and understanding how values are articulated and translated into actionable items. It helps identify the overarching vision, the strategies devised to achieve it, the specific objectives outlined, and the concrete actions proposed. Importantly, it also aims to highlight what is not present regarding justice in the written documents.

According to the thematic analysis done with the VSOA method, a total of 162 codes were devised. More important than the numbers is the balance between them. The analysed plan, although a document focused on actions (72%), shows a good balance of strategies (23%) and objectives (4%), with one overall aspirational vision (1%). The actions refer to the specific projects, policies, programs, and initiatives undertaken to achieve the stated strategies, objectives and, ultimately, the vision.

The main actions are mostly climate-focused, lacking a more direct social sustainability mention, and focusing on a material or service distribution.

The VSOA method highlighted the foundational aspects of the document, which now can be assessed by the framework built by the Spatial Justice Conceptual Model.

The DISTRIBUTIVE dimension shows a concern for the provision of benefits of climate adaptation, with the component "Fair Allocation" being mostly featured. The low number of "Access" and "Appropriation" demonstrate a disregard for "how the measures overcome fragmentation in the city or how residents might be able to transform the places and infrastructure being built.

The PROCEDURAL dimension shows a more present concern to the "Responsive Governance" component, and still many mentions that fit the "Adaptive Process" and "Democratic Engagement" components. It can be understood that there is a balance of measures for direct and mediate actions that influence how the city works.

The RECOGNITION dimension is rarely mentioned. Acknowledgement, validation, protection of individuals, collectives, and communities is not a priority. This is concerning, since climate action should target the most vulnerable and marginalised groups of the city otherwise it might reinforce injustices in the processes, policies, and response in the allocation of mitigation and adaptation measures.

In the analysed document, there is a "red flag", which is the absence of the components for "Care Practices" and "Foster Pluriverse", which provided an immediate score of "-3".

Considerations of "Access" and "Validation" scored higher, even though combined they account for only 10 mentions. The following example is a positive way to address the protection and care for a specific group, validating their livelihood, and coupling with their ease to reach amenities suited for them.

"Seniors can live independently into old age, with help and support including intensive nursing home care. [...] Smeetsen 9 Arma is an asset to Rotterdam and in particular to the elderly in Rotterdam. With all amenities, such as shops, public transport and hospital, so close by, the location is very suitable for this group."

Conclusion

At a glance:
 There is no explicit mention of Spatial Justice. However, many aspects were identified. Which point to the provision of public goods and the engagement of the population. Some of them have the potential to lead to a reinvention of relations, and the strengthening of local communities that care for the provision and build solidary networks.

The "levels of spatial justice" provided by the Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool are directly related to the Justice Readiness Level (JRL). The score in the JRL is the median of the scores of the dimensions. In the case of the analysed document, the score was "-0.55", which positions the JRL in between "Starting" and "Basic".

At this stage, it is possible to say that the document touches the necessity to pay greater attention to Spatial Justice concerns in its processes. There is a recognition of injustices and a beginning of efforts to address them. Initiatives may be in their infancy, and there may be limited awareness or understanding of the root causes of injustices. While there may be some attempts to mitigate disparities and promote fairness, Spatial Justice is not addressed frontly.

A negative point is the low balances and levels for the dimension and components of RECOGNITION, which should form the basis for transformative and just processes and provisions during urban sustainability transitions.

A positive point is the clarity of the document in communicating and acting its strategic vision. Even though indirect, many aspects have the potential to lead to a redistribution of green and blue structures in the built environment aligned with the engagement of local stakeholders, like residents and neighbourhood groups and initiatives.

Justice Readiness Level (JRL) is a complementary visual tool to monitor, visualise, and compare how justice is considered in decision-making. It aims to provide a shared understanding of justice considerations across many aspects of urban planning and design. Inspired by the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) method, the JRL provides a standard language that can be used across disciplines and organisations in order to better communicate and assess justice.

